

The Role of Paraphrase in Interpreting Students' Writing

Maya Lisa Aryanti, S. S. M. Hum

Abstract—To improve students' skill, writing is the most challenging skill to be developed. The reason is that besides helping the students to develop their skill, this activity also helps them to express themselves. This paper depicts how paraphrasing is very helpful to interpret students' writing. Syntactic units, used tenses and meanings will indeed change once the writings were paraphrased. The objectives of this research are to reveal the inappropriate structure of syntactic units, to show what types of sentences the students often make, and to show how paraphrasing can help to infer the message. The methodology of this research is descriptive qualitative research. In addition, theories of linguistics are also included. This includes theory of Syntax to describe syntactic units and tenses and theory of Semantics to describe theories of meaning and how paraphrasing works. The theories of general linguistics, grammar and writing are also provided to support the theories of Syntax and Semantics. The results of this research are concerned with how the message is received in the end. The message written in the students' essay is not clear because of the improper structure of syntactic units and use of incorrect of tenses. The students tend to use simple sentences, compound sentences and complex sentences with a few mistakes in their writing. In addition, they tend to create unnecessary phrases. The last point is that this research shows how paraphrase works to attain complete meaning of a sentence.

Keywords—Paraphrase, meanings, syntactic units and tenses.

I. INTRODUCTION

STUDENTS' writing is interesting because it can reveal much about their perceptions and understanding of a subject. In this study, students were asked to write an essay to understand how they constructed phrases, clauses and sentences and how they expressed their thoughts through their writing in English. This is an interesting research because the data of this research are taken from students' writing in which improper structure of syntactic units and the improper tenses can be recognised. Secondly, it is interesting to know the types of sentences used in students' writing because most of them tend to make simple sentences. Even if they tried to create either compound sentences or complex sentences, they often fail because of their mother tongue's influence. Thirdly, it is quite intriguing to know how the message can be inferred in the end.

The linguistic approach used in this research is descriptive approach. In this paper, there are 30 selected data which represent students' writing. Method is very crucial in any research because this reduces the researchers' burden during

their research. In general, there are two kinds of method: qualitative and quantitative. However, the writer only uses qualitative method for this research. According to [15, p.1], qualitative research exists because there is a change in paradigm in viewing reality/phenomena/symptoms.

It has already been mentioned before that the used technique is the qualitative one. Reference [14, p.3] states that "Qualitative gives directives in providing depth understanding of the social world of research participants through learning their social values, their experiences and perspectives."

The definition given by [13, p.29] is more helpful because the definition helps me to analyse the data. He says that a qualitative research not only uses non-numerical and unstructured data but also, typically, has research questions and methods. He adds that another method used interpretative description, allowing the writer to describe as well as interpret the signs used including dialogue and narration, camera shots, camera angles and movement, colour and lighting.

The techniques of data collection the writer uses are as:

1. The students were asked to write a free writing with English as their topic.
2. They were allowed to use various tenses which they considered suitable for their writing.
3. There are 150 data; however, only 30 data are selected to represent students' writing.

After the writer got all data the writer took secondary procedure in order to be able to analyse the data. The procedures are:

1. The writer reread the students' handwritings.
2. Students' handwritings were revised.
3. Students' handwritings and their revised handwritings were compared in order that the improper structure of the phrases, the improper structure of clauses and the improper structure of sentences can be found and sentence meaning finally can be conveyed.

II. THEORETICAL OUTLINE

A word is the smallest unit of a sentence and it has classification. The classification of words is called parts of speech. According to [3, p. 37], the most common parts of speech are nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and prepositions. Parts of speech tell us how a word is going to function in the sentence. However, [6, pp.2-4] states that there are eight parts of speech which are acknowledged. They are verb, noun, pronoun, adjective, adverb, preposition, conjunction and interjection.

- a) Verbs are words which expresses action or some other kind of event. For example: threw.

Maya Lisa Aryanti is with the University of Widyatama, Indonesia (e-mail: maya.lisa@widyatama.ac.id).

S.S. and M. Hum are with the University of Widyatama, Indonesia.

- b) Nouns are words functioning as a subject, object, or subjective complement in a central core. For example: boy, Mary, and girl.
- c) Pronouns are certain words that are used to avoid repeating a noun which has already been mentioned. For example: Instead of saying, *The boy threw the ball*, we can say, *He threw it*.
- d) Adjectives are words that modify the nouns. For example: big, green.
- e) Adverbs are words that modify the verb. For example: there, quickly.
- f) Preposition is a word that indicates a physical relationship between two other words.

For example: into.

- g) Conjunction is a word that connects words or groups of words that are equal grammatically (coordinate conjunction) and connects groups of words that are not equal grammatically (subordinate conjunction). For example: *and* (coordinate conjunction) and *after* (subordinate conjunction).
- h) Interjection is simply some expression of emotion or feeling (surprise, pleasure, pain, etc.) usually occurring at the beginning of the sentence and does not perform any grammatical function. For example: *oh, hurrah, ouch*.

To make a good writing, the students need to pay attention on diction. Diction is a word choice. According to Reference [17, p.116] diction refers to the lexical aspect of style and can simply mean the totality of lexical choices found in a given text or group of texts, but more often it refers to patterns of lexical choice, as when we speak of a writer's diction being "abstract" or "lofty."

In the students' writing, it was noticed that the students were trying to create some phrases. A phrase is a series of words which has meaning. Reference [4, p.222] states that a phrase is a grammatical unit which is in a form of predicative word combination, or normally it is known as word combination which fills one of syntactic function in a sentence whereas Reference [10, p. 17] states that phrase is applied only to sequences of more than a word. Reference [11, pp.128-131] classifies phrases into four types; noun phrases, prepositional phrases, verb phrases, and adverbial phrases whereas Reference [5, pp.67-70] classifies phrases into five; noun phrases, adjective phrases, adverbial phrases, prepositional phrases, and verb phrases.

A. Noun Phrases (NP)

Reference [11] defines noun phrases as words which are grouped altogether because all nouns are combined with determiners and adjectives to form larger phrases (for example: *the books* and *the controversial books* in English) whereas Reference [5, p. 68] describes a noun phrase as a constituent which has a noun as its head.

Phrase structure base Reference [17, p.133]: NP → (DET) N

Note: (DET) or determiners include the articles (a, an, the), the demonstratives or pointers (this, that, these, those), numerals (one, hundreds, five of), and quantifiers (many, some, some of).

B. Adjective Phrases

According to [5, p. 68], an adjective phrase is a constituent which has an adjective as its head. For example: very tall (*tall* is its head) and quite expensive (*expensive* is its head).

C. Adverbial Phrases

Adverbial phrases consist of adverbs and certain complement. For example: English adverbial phrases (*very early* and *very quickly*) [11]. According to [5, p. 69] describes an adverb phrase is a constituent which has an adverb as its head. For example: *very slowly* is an adverb phrase with *slowly* as its head.

D. Prepositional Phrases (PP)

Prepositional phrases are a combination between a preposition and a noun phrase (NP). For example: in the park [11]. According to Reference [5, p.69] a prepositional phrase is a constituent which has a preposition as its head. For example: *at the back* is a prepositional phrase with *at* as its head and *on Friday* is a prepositional phrase with *on* as its head.

Phrase structure Reference [17, p.134]: PP → PREP + NP

E. Verb Phrases

Verb phrases are the combination of verbs and noun phrases (NPs) or Prepositional Phrases (PPs). For example: *drop the ball* and *trip on the boat* [11]. Similarly, [17, p.134] states that at a minimum, the verb phrase consists of a main V(erb) and it may be followed by one NP (usually the traditional "object" relation, as in:

a. John **saw two bobcats**.

b. Bill **revved his motorbike**.

Phrase structure Reference [17, p.134]: VP → V(NP) (PP)

In some students' writing, it was clear that many of them had tried to make certain clauses. A clause is a group of structured words and has a verb [2, p.43], while [4, p.231] states that 'A clause is a syntactic unit which takes form of a series of predicative constructed words. It means that within the construction there is a component either in a form of a word or in a form of a phrase which is functioned as a subject, an object or a complement. Similarly, [6, p. 222] says that a clause consists of a subject and a predicate with finite verb. Further, [6, p.222] classifies clauses into two groups. They are main/independent clause and subordinating/dependent clauses. The independent clause is a full predication that may stand alone as a sentence (for example: John was sick; he didn't come to school), while the dependent clause has a special introductory word that makes the predication "depend" on an independent clause. For example: The student **who gets the highest grades** will receive an award. Here, **who gets the highest grades** modifies the noun **student**.

There are three types of dependent clauses which are often used in academic writing. They are adjective clauses, noun clauses and adverbial clauses. Adjective clauses modify nouns and pronouns. They begin with the words *who, whom, which, and that* [12, p.131]. A noun clause is used in the same ways as a noun and is used as a subject or an object. Words used to introduce noun clauses are *who, what, when, why, how, where,*

whether, that [1, p.263]. Adverbial clauses do not only modify verbs but also whole clauses. Some words used to introduce adverbial clauses are *because, when, although, as, if* [10, p.65], *before, after, while, as soon as, since, wherever* [12, p.101].

The highest level of syntactic unit is called a sentence. A sentence is a group of words that contains at least one subject and one verb and expresses a complete thought [12, p.11]. In English, there are four types of sentences. They are simple sentence, compound sentence, complex sentence and compound-complex sentence.

A simple sentence only has a full predicate in an independent clause [6, p.222] and only has one subject-verb pair [12, p.11] or a verb phrase [5, p. 86]. The subject tells who or what did something. The verb tells the action (*jump, work, think*) or condition (*is, was, seem, appear*) [12, p.11]. For example:

Filmmaker George Lucas has changed the film industry in many ways.

S V

One new technology was a special computer-assisted camera crane.

S V

The man stole the jewellery. [6, p.222]

S V

A compound sentence has two or more full predicate [6, p.223] and is composed of at least two simple sentences [12, p. 30] or more of equal status. Each of the clauses could potentially stand alone as an independent sentence [5, p. 86] joined by a comma and a coordinating conjunction [12, p. 30] or coordinators such as *and, but, or* [5, p.86] *so, for, nor, and yet* [12, p. 30]. For example:

The man stole the jewellery **and** he hid it in his home [6, p.223].

The gold disappeared with the mice, **so** the greedy man got nothing [12, p.30].

A complex sentence has two or more predicates [6, p.223] and consists of one clause that is inside another one [5, p.86]. In other words, a complex sentence is a combination of one independent clause and one (or more) dependent clause(s) [12, p.100]. Subordinators such as *that, if, and which* are used to link the clauses [5, p. 86]. For example: The man *who* stole the jewellery hid it in his home [6, p.223].

A compound-complex sentence contains at least three clauses and is both compound and complex [5] and [6]. For example: The man stole the jewellery *and* he hid it in his home *until* he could safely get out of town [6, p.223].

While making English sentences, tense, agreement, and punctuation also need to be considered. Tense is time marker and it indicates when some events take place and often shows chronology. In a syntactic sense, [10, p. 60] gives general description of tense; he said that tense has to do with whether the speaker or the writer uses a past-tense verb, for example *was* in *was listening*, and places a given event in past time, or a present tense verb, for example *is* in *is listening*, and places

the event in present time. Meanwhile, [5, p. 39] defines tense as the way the first verb in the verb phrase uses inflectional suffixes to indicate the occurrence of an event in time. According to this definition, there are two tenses in English: Present Tense and Past Tense. For example: 'I live in Singapore' means that at the time, when the speaker says the sentence, still resides in Singapore because the verb *live* is in the present tense. However, when the speaker says 'I lived in Singapore in 1992', it means that the event (living in Singapore) occurred in the past and is no longer true at the time the sentence is uttered. This can be seen from the use of *-ed* on the verb *live* to mark past tense. In semantic sense, tense involves locating what we talk about on an imaginary time line, of which the speaker is the reference point. The verb inflection *-ed* and the adverbs *yesterday, last week* all refer to points in the speaker's past at the time of utterance. If you read *yesterday* in a letter you have to know what day it was written and to know what day is referred to. Tense can be expressed in surface structures by verb inflections (typically *-s, -ed*), auxiliary verbs like *will* and *be going to*, adverbs like *now, then, tomorrow*, or even nothing at all, but it is always part of the underlying semantic structure of the sentence [17, p. 278].

Agreement between the subject and the verb (also known as concord) is the secondary aspect in writing which needs to be applied properly. To determine concord correctly, it is essential to identify the head of the subject. For example [5, p.41]:

1. My brother lives at home. The verb has an *-s* suffix, because the subject is singular.
2. My brothers live at home. The verb does not have a suffix because the subject is plural.
3. The teachers were grading assignments. The verb *be* exhibits subject-verb concord in the past tense.

It has been mentioned before that punctuation needs to be considered in writing. Generally, punctuation is a symbol used to describe how sentences should be arranged. Punctuation helps to deliver the meaning in writing. In modern English, punctuation often becomes the only way to show emphasis, or to show that you are asking a question [7, p. 154]. In addition, [4, pp.71-72] states that punctuations are signs which are used in written language in order that the sentences we write can be understood as it is intended to. Reference [7, pp.154-159] states that there are eleven types of punctuation. They are comma, full stop/period, question mark, exclamation point, semicolon, colon, hyphen, dash, apostrophe, capital letter and quotation marks. However, I only discuss briefly the comma, full stop/period, semicolon and capital letter. A comma is used to mark main clause from indefinite clause, to begin indefinite phrases, to begin a positive phrase, to separate clauses which are combined with *and, but, or, nor, for*, to begin an introductory clause and an introductory phrase, to separate certain parts in a group of words, phrases or clauses, and to mark the separation of direct utterances. A full stop or a period is used to end a sentence, to end an abbreviation, and to omit certain parts of a sentence. A semicolon is used to separate two sentences or two independent clauses that are closely related in meaning [1, p.308]. A capital letter is used to mark

the beginning of a sentence, to name a noun, to begin the first line of poetry, and to mark separation.

Words, phrases, clauses and sentences carry meaning. Reference [9, p.12] states that “Meaning, which is often called sense compared to reference, is something which can be understood from the word itself and can be separated from the use of context. Therefore, the meaning is not changed and it depends on the speaker.” There are many kinds of meaning but this section will discuss briefly three meanings which will be helpful while analysing the data. The first one is word meaning. It is a meaning which is a product of naming a thing by using language and is also called as senses [8, p.24]. The second is sentence (literal) meaning. The literal meaning of a sentence is based on just the semantic information that you have from your knowledge of English and is available without wondering who might say or write the words, when or where. No consideration of context is involved [8, p.6]. In addition, [17, p.187] describes sentence meaning as meaning relations that hold between morphemes and lexical items in a sentence.

While the students were expressing their thoughts in their writing, their mother tongue influenced their writing and their writings are authentic but mostly ambiguous. Therefore, it is important to paraphrase their sentences in order that complete and clear meaning can be conveyed. Reference [11, p. 271] states that two sentences that can have the same meaning are said to be paraphrases of each other. In addition, [8, p.29] states that paraphrase or pragmatic synonym, while [16, p. 149] refers to sentences with the same meaning, or another way of stating it or sentences that express the same proposition. The following examples given by [11, p. 271] describe how paraphrasing works:

1. Two police chased the burglar. → Paraphrase form: The burglar was chased by the police.
2. It is unfortunate that the team lost. → Paraphrase form: Unfortunately, the team lost.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

Data 1

I was the second child from a 3 siblings, my older brother is ghaniy giovanni and my sister is gisza gabriella.

Analysis

The student uses a wrong verb to describe his status within his family. He should write ‘I **am** the second child of three siblings’ because ‘I was the second child from a 3 siblings’ means he is the second child in the past but now he becomes either the first or the last child. The second mistake is that he does not use capitalization while writing his siblings’ names. He should write *Ghany Giovanni* and *Gisza Gabriella*. The type of sentence he uses is a compound sentence.

Data 2

In future I want to owner of filmmaker or production House.

Analysis

The student made two mistakes in his simple sentence. The first is that his attempt to make a prepositional phrase. He

writes *infuture*. It should be *in the future*. The second mistake is the use of noun ‘owner.’ He should write ‘own’ (verb).

Data 3

My motivasion for choose this management business, I want to learn more about, how the right business management. Then as a stepping-stone to entering the workforce, so that it still associated with the business. and the last one I would like to becoming a wealthy businessman and I look forward to graduating with the best value with the right time.

Revision

My motivation to choose management business is that I want to learn more about how business management works and what the business management looks like. Business management is considered as a stepping-stone to enter the workforce because it still relates to business. I would like to become a wealthy businessman. I look forward to graduating with the best mark and on time.

Analysis

It is clear that the student had tried to make a compound-complex sentence. He uses ‘and’ to mark a compound sentence and both noun clauses and an adverbial clause even if he failed. This can be seen from noun clause marker ‘that’ and adverbial marker ‘because’. In addition, he also uses improper diction and incorrect spelling.

Data 4

Next week I am going to *Mesir* with my family. We have traveled by plane. When, I was there I want to see *Piramid*, and I want eat *Mesir* cuisine.

Analysis

The student who writes this sentence makes mistakes when using tenses to describe chronological events. In addition, she uses Bahasa Indonesia to describe a country and a monument, as well as inappropriate placement of punctuation. She should write:

Next week I am going to Egypt with my family. We will travel by plane. While I am there I want to see the pyramids and I want to eat Egyptian cuisine.

This student uses two types of sentences. The first is a simple sentence and the second one is compound-complex sentence.

Data 5

Now I’am must study english language because I’am think studying english language very important to me.

Revision

Now I must study English because it is very important for me to learn it.

Analysis

The verbs are double (*am must* and *am think*).

Data 6

Everyday I am always watch anime and Read manga, its very fun. My favorite anime is “Kimi ni Todoke”. It’s a romance anime and my favorite manga is Namida Usagi. I have read 3 manga in 1 hours.

Revision

Every day I watch *anime* and *read* manga because it is very fun. My favourite anime is “Kimi ni Todoke”, which is a romance *anime*, and my favourite manga is *Namida Usagi*. I have read three *mangas* in 1 hour.

Analysis

Double verbs, improper use of capitalization and punctuation.

Data 7

I like music and dance art. is dance hiphop dance. I have in this instructure dance. I came to dance art. in this campus. I will is dance art a professional.

Revision

I like music and dance. My favourite dance is hip hop and I have a dance instructor. I joined a dance community at this campus. I want to be a professional dancer.

Analysis

The subject in the second sentence is missing and the student also makes a wrong sentence with the verb ‘have’. The next mistake is incorrect diction and the last one, in the last sentence there are two verbs that none of them describes what subjects do.

Data 8

I watches the tv in the evening. I has watched a sport. Yesterday, I watched comedy station. Maybe I’ll stay home and watch television tonight.

Revision

I watch television in the evening. I watch sport. Yesterday, I watched a comedy program. Maybe I’ll stay home and watch television tonight.

Analysis

Subject and verb in the first and second sentence do not suit to each other. In the second sentence, sport does not need ‘a’ because it is an uncountable noun. In addition, this student chooses incorrect diction; on television, comedy is used to describe a genre of programming.

Data 9

Last year I am going to be musician and session player for live music and recording. Now I study music on youtube, and future I will to have home studio.

Revision

Last year I became a musician and a session player for live music and recording. Now, I am learning music on Youtube, and in the future, I will have home studio.

Analysis

In the first sentence the used verb (am going to) does not fit to the adverb of time ‘last year’ and in the main clause after conjunction ‘and’ there is a mistake when the student uses the verb phrase to describe the future. The verb phrase is written ‘will to have’ instead of ‘will have’.

Data 10

a couple weeks ago I have an interesting dream in my sleep but I can’t remember what’s dream about. I always reading a book or playing a game while drink a cup of tea.

Revision

A couple of weeks ago I had an interesting dream, but when I woke I couldn’t remember what it was about. I always read a book or play a game while drinking a cup of tea.

Analysis

In the first main clause, the used verb (have) does not fit to the adverb of time (a couple of weeks ago) and in the second main clause after conjunction ‘but’ the used verb (can’t) also does not fit to the adverb of time. Next, the writer also makes a mistake while forming the noun clause. It is written ‘what’s dream about’ instead of ‘what the dream (it) was about.’

Data 11

Two weeks ago I go to Bandung Japan Festival. In there was so many competition like cosplay competition, dance cover, sing cover and many more.

Revision

Two weeks ago I went to Bandung Japan Festival. There were many competitions like the cosplay competition, dance cover, sing cover and many more.

Analysis

There are two simple sentences that were written. In the first sentence, the used verb does not fit to the adverb (two weeks ago) and in the second sentence, the verb ‘was’ does not agree to the inverted subject ‘so many competition’.

Data 12

To make animation sometimes it’s hard, but sometimes it’s easy it depends our will.

Revision: It is a creative process to make animation. Therefore, it’s sometimes either hard or easy. It depends on our skill.

Analysis

The students should write *to make animation it’s either hard or easy* because the sentence shows the student’s view about animation. He also should make ‘it depends our skill’ as a new sentence. The verb phrase ‘depends’ is not followed by preposition ‘on’ which should be added.

Data 13

Have you imagined about your future? It’s important to do. Because imagined about your future will make you to plan your habit.

Revision

Have you thought about your future? It’s important to think about your future, because doing so will help you plan for it.

Analysis

The first problem in the student’s writing is the incorrect use of capitalization; the ‘B’ in *because* should not be capitalized and it should connect two sentences. The second problem is that the student should put a gerund as the subject of a sentence followed by a noun phrase instead of a participle followed by a prepositional phrase.

Data 14

This morning Date 17 I wake up and thinking about something and searching for *jalan keluar*. but I not find everything good. and I go out from my room and take deep

breath for refresh my mind.

Revision

This morning, I woke up, thought about something and searched for solution but I did not find anything. Then, I left my room and took deep breath to refresh my mind.

Analysis

The date should not have been written because it is unacceptable to write a date without a month. The student uses wrong verb when he describes his first activity (wakes up), the second activity (a thought) and the last one (a search). Next, it seems he tries to construct a compound sentence but it fails because it does not connect directly. There is a period before the conjunction *but*, and the verb phrase in the main clause located after it is not correct because there is no *be* in past form to indicate a past event. Further, it seems that he tries to make a compound sentence; this can be seen from the conjunction '*and*' which he uses. However, he actually does not need to add '*and*' because it can be replaced by '*next*' to describe the order of an event. In this new sentence, he uses the wrong verb and he should write '*to refresh*' instead of '*for refresh*'.

Data 15

Every monday morning at 7 am o'clock I study general english. I have eaten bread. Before, I went go to widyataman. I bring my young brother to he's school. Then I will be late to university of widyatama.

Revision

Every Monday morning at 7 o'clock I study General English. Before I go to Widyataman, where I attend the University of Widyatama, I eat my toast and take my younger brother to school, and then I am running late to class.

Analysis

The writer uses three time markers; Monday morning, 'A.M.' and 'o'clock' and does not capitalize proper nouns, such as the name of the course (General English) and the university (University of Widyatama). So, these are considered as wrong. Next, it seems the student tries to construct a complex sentence and tries to describe a chronological event even if it is wrong because he puts a period before conjunction *before*, capitalizes it and gives a comma after it. The chronological order of events is also considered as a fail because the verb in the main class is in a form of present perfect tense instead of the past perfect. In addition, the diction is also incorrect and what he means is that he accompanies his younger brother to school.

Data 16

I am junior Graphic designer and worked as a freelancer at RMHR.

Revision: I am a junior graphic designer and work as a freelancer at RMHR.

Analysis

The only mistake in this writing is the use of tenses. The students should write '*work*' instead of '*worked*'.

Data 17

I am studying graphic Designer. I started it since 2009. in

my dream, I want to be the most Designer. and for realitation I am studied with earnest.

Revision

I am studying Graphic Design. I have been studying it since 2009. I want to be a top designer and I study hard to make it a reality.

Analysis

The student should capitalize G and D in *graphic design* because it is a name of a course. He uses the wrong verb when he intends to describe the activity he is undertaking, which has begun from a point in the past to the moment he writes. He does not put an adjective after the adverb '*most*'. It seems that he tries to make a compound sentence even if he fails because he puts a period before conjunction '*and*'. In the main clause, after the conjunction *and*, he writes double verbs and he made an unnecessary prepositional phrase just like the one he wrote before the main clause *I want to be the most....* and after the verb *studied*.

Data 18

I was studying General English last year. My value for this lesson is complicated that hard to be understand.

Revision

I studied General English last year. My grade was bad because it is a complicated lesson that is hard to understand.

Analysis

After the sentences were paraphrased, many changes were made. In the first sentence, the student used the past continuous tense. After it was paraphrased, its tense is changed into a verb used to express past activity. There is a change in diction as well ('*value*' is replaced by '*grade*'). There is an omission in a phrase and there is a new phrase in the second sentence which is paraphrased. There is a prepositional phrase '*for this lesson*' in the student's second sentence and it is omitted in the second sentence after it was paraphrased. The word '*lesson*' in the paraphrased sentence is put after the word '*complicated.*' Thus, a new noun phrase was created.

The second sentence written by the student contains no conjunction. However, in the second sentence, which is paraphrased, the conjunction '*because*' is added to make the meaning of the sentence clearer.

Data 19

I beg to be able to speak english in order for me understand.

Revision: I want to be able to understand English so that I can speak it.

Analysis

This student uses incorrect diction. The student should use '*want*' instead of '*beg*' and should capitalize the proper noun, '*English*'. In addition, the conjunction used to connect the sentences is also wrong. It should be written as '*so that*'.

Data 20

I have been lecturing the students since August 2016 in Widyatama Accounting faculty diploma. I like English butt I can't understand that leasone. I will try learning so that I can understand and will better.

Revision

I have been a student of Accounting at Widyatama University since August 2016. I like English but I can't understand the lessons. I will try to learn it so that I can understand and my English will get better.

Analysis

This student cannot manage her sentence properly. In addition, she often uses incorrect spelling for English words like 'butt' for 'but' and 'leason' for 'lessons'. Further, she uses a gerund where she should have used infinitive form. In her last sentence, she should use verb phrase to express the future properly.

Data 21

My name is Nurul. I'm first son from two daughter. My younger sister name is Hanifah that still class two in Elementary School. I born in date 14 August 1995 at Kebumen, East Java. My activity in this case is studying at *Universitas Widyatama* because I didn't accept in *Politeknik Negeri Bandung*. Location of Universitas Widyatama isn't so far from my home. I going to do after my graduation from *Universitas Widyatama* is searching worker. I want to be great *Akuntan* in the future.

Revision

My name is Nurul. I'm the eldest of two daughters. My younger sister's name is Hanifah and she is still in second grade in Elementary School. I was born on August 14th, 1995 in Kebumen, East Java. I am currently studying at University of Widyatama which is located close to my home, because I didn't get accepted into Bandung State Polytechnic. When I graduate from university I will search for a job. I want to be a successful accountant one day.

Analysis

She is wrong when referring herself as a son because she is a young woman. She uses the wrong language to describe her position within her family. 'I'm the first son from two daughters' means I'm the first son and the descendant of two daughters who were married to each other. In the next sentence, she does not use an apostrophe where she should to express possession (my little sister's name'). Further, she should write *and* instead of *that* and should rewrite the subject and the verb. She should write *in the second grade* instead of *class two*. When describing when she was born, the author uses the wrong verb phrase structure; she should write 'I was born' instead of 'I born'. Next, she made unnecessary prepositional phrases ('in date' and 'in this case'). She should write 'I am currently studying at University of Widyatama' because she was learning while she was writing this sentence; and she should write 'I didn't get accepted into Bandung State Polytechnic.' instead of 'I didn't accept in Bandung State Polytechnic.' It seems she tries to make a noun clause even if it is wrong. She writes 'I going to do after my graduation from Universitas Widyatama is searching worker' instead of 'When I graduate from university I will search for a job.' She confuses an employee and an employer. An employee is someone who works, whereas an employer is a person or company who pays/hires someone/people to work for them.

The author uses non-English words, 'I want to be great *Akuntan* in the future' should be written as 'I want to be a successful accountant one day.'

Data 22

My name is Putri. **I'm born** in **bekasi** 3 may 1995. I **live** at Sindanglaya. **I'm have** acivity after **graduation** senior high school and I **will** study at **widyatama** university. I'm choose **widyatama** university because **widyatama** university is a good campus and I **not accept** in PTN. after graduation in **widyatama** university I wish **can working** in Bank.

Revision

My name is Putri. I **was born** in **Bekasi** on May 3rd, 1995. I **live** in Sindanglaya. After I graduated from senior high school, I **will** study in University of **Widyatama**. I chose **it** because it is a good campus and because I **was not accepted** into PTN (National College). I want to work in a bank when I graduate from University of Widyatama.

Analysis

Most of the author's mistakes are related to the use of tenses and verb phrases. In addition, she does not capitalize proper nouns, *B* in Bekasi and *W* and *U* in Widyatama University. She was trying to make a compound-complex sentence. 'I'm have activity' was omitted because she did not specify her activity.

Data 23

English is one of the universal **language**. We can get more knowledge by mastering English because **so many importants book written by English**. **Besaide** that we can chat with foreign people from **the other country**, **english** makes people more confidence. In Indonesia English can be learned by **children eight years old**.

Revision

English is one of the universal **languages**. We can gain more knowledge by mastering English because **many important books are written in English**. **Besides** that, **English** makes people more confident and we can chat with people from **other countries**. In Indonesia, English can be learned by **eight year old children**.

Analysis

This student should write languages instead of language. There is an attempt to make noun phrases (e.g.: so many importants book, the other country, and children eight years old), to construct a prepositional phrase (Besaide that) and to make a complex sentence (e.g: because so many importants book written by English) even if they all are wrong. In addition, this student also incidentally writes English with a small 'e'.

Data 24

In my house I **always teaching** English to my friend. I never **stop learn** English. we can learn english **not only from book but we can learn English by watching the movie** or listening to the music.

Revision

In my house I **always teach** English to my friend. I never **stop learning** English. We can learn English **not only from**

books but also from movies. In addition, we can also learn from listening to some music.

Analysis

There are three mistakes made in the text. The first is the use of verb to express the present tense. The student should write 'teach' instead of 'teaching'. The second is the use of a gerund (learning) after the verb 'stop' instead of a base formed verb (learn). The last one is parallelism (noun phrase parallelism). In her writing, the student tries to construct a parallel structure of a noun phrase and a clause in which there is another form of parallelism (gerund after preposition parallelism). Her writing could have been better if she had constructed another sentence after the noun phrase parallelism.

Data 25

I know learning English **should slowly**. I've **scared** when it learn **english** because it is difficult to understand.

Revision

I know learning English is a slow process. I find learning it scary because it is difficult to be understand.

Analysis

There are three mistakes in this text. The first is the verb phrase; the word *should* needs to be followed another verb and she did not add any verb behind *should*. The second mistake is the use of tenses. She should write: 'I find it scary' instead of 'I've scared.' The third is the capitalization for proper nouns. The writer does not write English with *e* in a capital letter.

Data 26

I know that learning **english should slowly**. I haven't learned **english 6 months**. I have **to learning english for a long time**. I need **tutoring and** I can understand. In campus **actually want to hone learning English**, but **I have'nt understand** because my teacher failed to give a **detailed explanation**.

Revision

I know that learning **English should be done slowly**. I haven't studied **English for six months**. I have **to study English intensely**. I need **a tutor who** I can understand. Actually, I want to hone learning English at university, but **I can't understand** because my lecturer is unable to give **detailed explanation**.

Analysis

The author does not capitalize the proper noun, English and the word *should* needs another verb to follow it. The writer should add *for* before a noun phrase (six months) and she should avoid constructing an unnecessary prepositional phrase (for a long time) in order to avoid misunderstanding. The phrase 'for a long time' represents the duration of time, so it only fits to present perfect. She should add either a noun phrase or an infinitive verb instead of a gerund (tutoring) and she should construct a complex sentence instead of compound one. Finally, she seems to try to construct a compound-complex sentence even though it is incorrect. In the main clause before the conjunction *but*, there is no subject and she should write 'I can't understand' instead of 'I haven't understand'. Her attempt to construct a noun phrase (a detailed

explanation) is quiet good.

Data 27

I have known **english since grade four**. until now I am learning english **so many things I can't understand of english such as like simple present. Present perfect and simple past besides that I can't different which one is adjective but I try to understand. I want master english** and now I will study more of **english**. When I was in senior high school **english** is easier than now, **because in campus there is so many brance of english. It makes me difficult to understand what the teacher teach**. When **I was exam I was studying english hard** and I hope I can get good score in **english**.

Revision

I have studied **English since I was in the fourth grade** (alternatively, **since I was a fourth grader**). I **can't understand many things in English such as simple present, present perfect and simple past. Besides that, I can't differentiate between an adjective and a noun but I will try to understand. I want to master English** and I will continue to study **it**. When I was in senior high school, **English** was easier than it is now. **It is difficult for me to understand the lectures on campus because many subjects are taught in English**. I will study hard for the English exam and hope I get a good grade.

Analysis

The author does not capitalize the proper noun, English, as well the incorrect use of punctuation. The student tried either to construct a complex sentence or to make a prepositional phrase. She constructs an unnecessary adverbial clause because her learning process can be implied in the first sentence. In the next sentence, the subject of the sentence is not clear (whether it is 'many things' or 'I') and the author adds an unnecessary preposition to specify examples. In addition, she used adjective 'different' instead of the verb 'differentiate' after modal verb 'can'. In the clause after 'but' she should use future tense instead of simple present to describe her efforts. She should add 'to' after the verb 'want' and she should omit 'now' when she talks about her future plans. It will be better to say 'it is difficult for me to understand.....' than 'it makes me difficult to understand...'. There is a mistake in S-V agreement of the sentence placed after 'because'. 'There is so many branches of english' should be 'many subjects are taught in English'. She is successful in constructing a noun clause, but subject-verb agreement used is not correct. The adverbial clause 'When I was exam....' in 'When I was exam I was studying english hard' sounds awkward because the verb *was* describes 'a state', 'a characteristic' or 'an identity'. Thus, adverbial clause 'When I was exam' suggests that in the past, she was a thing. Meanwhile, in the main clause, she should have written 'I will study hard for the English exam.'

Data 28

Although **english didn't used in my country** but I was **falling** in love to this language. I always **singing** the **song**

used english language. It has **helped me so easy my experience in the** vocabularies.

Revision

Although **English isn't spoken in my country**, I fell in love with the language. I always **sing** along to **English songs**; it has **helped** me to improve my vocabulary.

Analysis

The student tries to construct a complex sentence but she fails because in her writing and in the first line there is no main clause. Next, she should write English with 'E' in capital letter and she uses wrong tense and verb phrase. The author is an Indonesian whose native language is Bahasa Indonesia and who is still learning English, and therefore, she should write 'English isn't spoken in my country' instead of 'english didn't used in my country.' In addition, she also uses past continuous about how she feels about English and this is incorrect. She should write 'I fell in love with this language' instead of 'I **was falling** in love to this language.' In the next sentence, the verb of the sentence is not clear and there is an attempt to construct an adjective clause (the song used english language) even if the adjective clause is not necessary. She should write I always **sing** along to **English songs** instead of 'I always singing'. In her last sentence, she should add an infinitive form after the object pronoun 'me' because the verb 'help' is usually followed by an infinitive.

Data 29

In my opinion **english very important** for students. **Because english usefull** in activity. **But** students **not understands** english because **he's not** study. In university I **studying english** and I like **english**. I **studying english** since **elementary school** and I always study hard english literature. But I don't understand about gerund and infinitive.

Revision

In my opinion, **English is very important** for students **because it is a useful** activity. **However**, students **do not understand** English because **they do not** study. In university, I **am studying English** and I like **it**. I **have been studying English** since **I was in elementary school**. I always study English literature but I don't understand about gerunds and infinitives.

Analysis

The first two clauses actually can be combined into a complex sentence, and in this sentence, each clause should have a verb. It would be better for the author to began the sentence with the transition, 'however' instead of the conjunction, 'but'. Afterwards, she needs to pay attention to the verb phrase used in the main clause; it should read 'students **do not understand** English' instead of 'students **not understands** english'. Another point which she needs to pay attention to is the use of a suitable pronoun. In the original text, it is unclear to whom 'he' refers to. In the next sentence, she should write 'In university, I **am studying English** and I like **it**' instead of 'In university I **studying english** and I like **english**.' Lastly, she should construct two complete sentences to describe her situation instead of constructing two incomplete sentences, one of which has an incomplete verb

phrase and the other a separated clause.

Data 30

Now I have to **start** like **English language**. I think studying **english language** very important **to me**. After I've **finished** my studied. I hope that I've learned I can use **in the workplace**.

Revision

I have to **start** to like **English** now. I think studying **English** is very important **for me**. After I **finish** my studies, I hope I can use what I have learned **in the workplace**.

Analysis

The author should omit 'language' in 'English language' because English refers to language, culture and people. In her next sentence, she needs to add a verb after the word English and the preposition used should be 'for' instead of 'to'. The last lines should combine both clauses; the sentence should read 'After I **finish** my studies, I hope I can use what I have learned **in the workplace**.' In the original text, the author uses present perfect rather than simple present tense to describe what she wants to do in the near future and she constructs an unnecessary noun clause after the word 'that'. In addition, there is no object after the verb 'use' in her writing.

IV. CONCLUSION

Students often make mistakes in forming phrases. Incorrect structure of syntactic units and improper use of tenses affect the meaning of the message; they result in ambiguous or confused meaning and disorder of chronological events. A number of students attempt to construct compound sentences, complex sentences and compound-complex sentences with a number of mistakes. Paraphrasing is needed to reform the meaning of the sentence and it is made in the revision section. In this section, paraphrasing may occur by adding and/or omitting some parts of speech or some phrases or even clauses. Changing either diction or tenses is also possible. When paraphrasing, it is important to know and to understand the structure of phrases and sentences and how they can be formed. The importance of this study is to show how paraphrase works to attain the complete meaning of a sentence.

REFERENCES

- [1] Azar, *Understanding and Using English Grammar*, 2nd ed. New Jersey, United States of America: Prentice-Hall, Inc, 1989.
- [2] Burling, Robbins, *Pattern of Language*, Academic Press, 1992.
- [3] Carnie, Andrew, *Syntax. A Generative Introduction*, 2nd ed. Australia: Blackwell Publishing, 2007.
- [4] Chaer, Abdul, Drs., *Linguistik Umum*. Jakarta, PT Rineka Cipta, 2003
- [5] Deterding and Poedjosoedarmo, *The Grammar of English, Morphology and Syntax for English Teachers in Southeast Asia*, Singapore: Prentice Hall Pearson Education Asia Pte Ltd, 2001.
- [6] Frank, Marcella, *Modern English*, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc, 1972.
- [7] Gatherer, W.A., *The Student's Handbook of Modern English*, Jakarta: PT Gramedia, 1986.
- [8] Griffiths, Patrick, *An Introduction to English Semantics and Pragmatics*, Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press. Ltd, 2006.
- [9] Hofmann, Th.R., *Realms of Meaning: An Introduction to Semantics*, New York: Longman Group Limited, 1993.
- [10] Miller, Jim, *An Introduction to English Syntax*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh

University Press, 2002.

- [11] O'Grady, Dobrovolsky, Katamba, *Contemporary Linguistics, An Introduction*. New York: St. Martin's Press, Inc, 1989.
- [12] Oshima and Hogue, *Introduction to Academic Writing*, 3rd ed. New York, United States of America: Pearson Education, Inc, 2007.
- [13] Punch, Keith F, *Introduction to Social Research: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. London: Sage Publications Ltd, 1998.
- [14] Ritchie, Lewis and Jane, *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*, Great Britain: The Cromwell Press Ltd, 2003.
- [15] Sugiyono, *Memahami Penelitian Kualitatif*, Bandung: CV Alfabeta, 2007.
- [16] Tannen, Deborah, *Gender and Discourse*, New York, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994.
- [17] Traugott and Pratt, *Linguistics for Students of Literature*, New York, United States of America: Harcourt Brace, Jovanovich, Inc, 1980.